

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Piano Performance Analysis Using Technique Information Extracted from Videos

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Abstract

Piano technique is an important aspect of the performance and learning of the musical instrument and requires an understanding of the physical and visual processes of performance. Many of the elements of a performance will be influenced by the pianist's technique, which can include limitations such as their skill, hand size, and finger dexterity. As such, understanding technique can enhance many applications in piano, including skill assessment and movement suggestions for education, more realistic generative models based on the constraints/movement of hands, refining the classification range in polyphonic pitch estimation by modelling the hand placement on the piano and estimating the most efficient or desirable fingers for a sequence of notes, among many other applications. We present a generalized pipeline for extracting hand movement information from piano performance videos and demonstrate the creation of a dataset from YouTube videos. An analysis is performed on the created dataset and outlines the accuracy in extracting technique information using the given hand-pose estimation and transcription models. We then train an autoregressive graph neural network using this new dataset for the task of Automatic Piano Fingers (APF) and benchmark the performance in comparison with state-of-the-art models. Limitations to automatic technique extraction from videos are discussed, and a series of feature improvements are documented to improve the next iterations of this dataset.

Keywords: Audio-Visual Datasets; Hand-Pose Estimation; Automatic Piano Fingering; Neural Networks

Chapter 1

Introduction

Piano technique can be reflected in the physical capabilities employed by a pianist to realize the intended performance. It is a set of skills that are refined over years of practice and can include aspects such as finger speed movement, pedal usage, and dynamic sensitivity, among others. As such, it is one of the primary indicators for piano learning [1], and an improvement in technique would validate that the provided education and/or practice regimen is effective for the pianist.

In creating a system to understand piano technique information, analyzing only audio data lends limited information. Note sequences and dynamics can be measured, but aside from this, piano technique is largely a physically driven skill and requires knowledge of hand movements. Creating a multimodal dataset that incorporates video-extracted information would open many opportunities to explore piano techniques further. This could have a large impact on many fields of research. In piano education, technique understanding could be used to assess the skill of the learner and to provide suggestions to improve performance, such as which fingers to use for a note sequence, when to employ piano techniques such as a hand-turnover, and individual modelling based on the size of the performer's hand. Generative models could also be developed based on such audio-visual data, for applications such as music generation with an understanding of the limitations of hands to create a more realistic and playable composition, as well as hand-pose generation. Piano transcrip-

tion could also be improved by refining the frame classification range in polyphonic pitch estimation by modelling the hand placement on the piano, in other words removing the option to predict notes that wouldn't be possible given the size of the hands and the fingers that are already being used. Tasks such as piano performance difficulty analysis [2] could also be improved with added hand-pose features in the dataset.

The task of piano fingering is a subset of piano technique and is a complex and situation-dependent task, where the performer must choose the correct finger order to execute a sequence in the piece. The choice of the finger will be dependent on many factors, including expertise, physical limitations, creative decisions, and more. An optimal chosen sequence of notes may aim to minimize the difficulty and hand movement while maximizing articulation control. Even among professional pianists, there will be multiple interpretations of the correct fingering of a given sequence. An automatic piano fingering labelled dataset that contains annotations of the same piece from multiple experts shows that on average, 60-80% of the fingering choices are agreed upon [3]. Automatic Piano Fingering (APF) is the challenge of providing a system capable of predicting accurate finger annotations for a given input piece. The quality of these annotations is not trivial to assess, given the subjectivity of piano fingering as previously discussed. Systems built for this task [3, 4] need finger-labelled note sequences to train estimation models and have outlined the need for an expanded dataset to improve results.

Given the wide availability of video piano performance data online, notably on platforms such as YouTube, a generalized pipeline can be developed to extract piano technique information using hand-pose estimation. We show that this pipeline can be used to create a large-scale multimodal dataset for piano technique, one application of which can be automatic piano fingering.

In this work, we release an open-source implementation of this proposed pipeline ¹, demonstrating that it can be used on videos from different performers and recording environments with various lighting conditions. With the pipeline, the proposed

¹Code available at: <https://github.com/sjcantor/piano-hands-technique-extraction>

dataset can be reproduced, expanded upon, or used with completely new data. We analyze the created dataset and outline the limitations and options for enhancing the data and increasing the dataset size. Using previously defined autoregressive neural networks [4], we train and test a model for the task of automatic piano transcription and discuss the results.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Action Recognition

The task of analyzing piano performance from videos using hand tracking is considered an action recognition task, which can be defined by the higher-level goal of classifying and capturing meaningful information from human actions using computer vision. Previous works include discriminative models [5, 6] to perform classification on action datasets [7], while others use feature extraction to train generative models on actions [8, 9].

While systems and datasets for action recognition are commonly general-purpose, including actions such as running, shaking hands, hugging, etc., there are applications more related to the aim of this thesis, including audio, music and hand-related works. Xu et al. present a motion generation system from speech to estimate accompanying hand gestures and body motion from audio [8]. Even more closely related to our task, Je et al. use hand tracking to estimate tempo and time signature information using gesture recognition, the center of gravity in hand movement, and vector movements in relation to classical conducting theory [10].

2.2 Sequence Models

Piano melodies, their associated fingerings, and musical compositions are all sequential-based input. When considering a system to predict/generate series data such as this, there are several sequence models to consider. Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) have been a long-standing statistical method to generate a series of outputs using several hidden probabilities and have proven to be effective in many applications with time-series data, including speech recognition [11].

Sequence models have become the primary tool used for finger label prediction in active automatic piano fingering research. In note sequences, the first note may start with any finger depending on the performer's choice, but following notes are highly dependent on past finger assignments in the sequence. High-order Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) can utilize this sequence-based data and have even been demonstrated to perform well on the specific task of automatic piano fingering [3], even outperforming a deep-neural network-based approach on the same dataset.

With the introduction of deep neural networks (DNNs), sequenced-based models including Long Short-Term Memory [12] could be adapted to utilize the powerful performance of these DNNs and demonstrate their effectiveness on the complex sequence task of language translation [13]. Applied to the task of automatic piano fingering, Recurrent Neural Networks have demonstrated their effectiveness in modelling finger sequences [14]. Initially, simple neural networks were applied but were not able to outperform the Hidden Markov Models proposed in the same research [3]. Later, a bi-directional long short-term memory (BI-LSTM) neural network was applied as a local classification problem to predict a single label in a note sequence, surrounded by labelled notes on each side [14]. This is effective based on the strong correlation between neighbouring fingerings. The model proposed by [14] cannot support polyphonic input (multiple notes at the same time), and so proposes a post-processing step to apply fingers to chords based on certain rules. Despite this, it does not achieve the same performance results as the HMMs proposed by [3] on the same test set.

Figure 1: ArGNN with GNN Encoder [4]

Ramonedá et al. present an autoregressive model to predict a new sequence of finger labels, which outperforms the previously proposed HMMs on the same test dataset [4]. As seen in Figure 1, the encoder could also be switched from an LSTM to a graph-neural network to give improved results, as it better models the polyphonic relationship between notes by marking them as edges in the graph.

2.3 Piano Performance Datasets

There have been several datasets analyzing piano performances. We will discuss the different data representations in these works and their application in understanding piano technique with comparison to the task of automatic piano fingering and our proposed dataset for multimodal piano performance analysis with hand-pose estimation.

The MAESTRO dataset is a large collection of audio virtuosic piano performances with fine alignment MIDI files and contains around 200 hours of data [15]. It is

an especially valuable dataset for evaluating and training models for the task of polyphonic piano transcription. As such, it will be used to compare the effectiveness of transcription models that will be implemented in this thesis to extract note sequences from the audio component of the YouTube performances. However, this dataset cannot be used for the task of automatic piano fingering, as neither the audio nor MIDI component contains information regarding fingering. Accompanying sheet music with fingerings or video performances with the hands visible would be needed to enhance such a dataset for the task.

The MAPS dataset [16] contains a similar collection to the MAESTRO dataset [15] and is sometimes the preferred dataset to train/evaluate models for piano transcription. This will depend on the model, and so to compare them more accurately for the task in our thesis, they are evaluated on our own set of performances, those that contain an accompanying MIDI that can be used as a ground-truth label.

Another aspect of piano performance technique is understanding the difficulty of a piece. The Mikrokosmos-Difficulty dataset is a collection of 147 pieces that are each classified by difficulty [2]. Ramoneda et al. implement a Gated Recurrent Unit neural network (GRU) and gradient-boosted trees to classify pieces trained on the dataset and demonstrate that input features, which are in the format of symbolic music representation for this paper, preprocessed with piano fingering, lead to better results when training a classification model. The piano fingering was generated for the input scores using a Hidden Markov Model [3], indicating that a more accurate algorithm for piano fingering classification would also improve results in the task of piano performance difficulty classification.

2.3.1 Automatic Piano Fingering Datasets

The construction of the PIG Dataset is the first known large-scale piano fingering dataset and consists of 150 pieces with annotations by one or more expert pianists [3]. Despite being the first, it sets the standard for benchmarking models for the task due to the quality of the labelling. It is a fully labelled dataset that was carefully created by hand, and the multiple annotations per piece allow for a more thorough

$$Precision = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T TP(t)}{\sum_{t=1}^T TP(t) + FP(t)} \quad (1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T TP(t)}{\sum_{t=1}^T TP(t) + FN(t)} \quad (2)$$

$$F\text{-measure} = \frac{2 \times precision \times recall}{precision + recall} \quad (3)$$

Figure 2: Calculating the F-Measure of a transcription [18]

evaluation of models. Since piano fingering does not have a single solution per sequence, measuring an accuracy over a set of pieces with only one pianist’s fingerings will only reward the model that overfits to the pianist’s personal preferences, instead of a more generalized solution that will work for other performances.

The Thumbset Dataset was built afterwards, which contains 2523 pieces [4]. The finger labels are applied using partial annotations from sheet music and thus are not expert labelled as compared to [3] but expand on the work of automatic piano transcription and demonstrate that models trained on partial annotations and finetuned on the FIG dataset could achieve state-of-the-art results.

The Automatic Piano Fingering Dataset was created using video and MIDI data from the YouTube creator Rousseau [17]. Using computer vision to detect the hands and piano in a video, it could automatically assign fingers to MIDI note sequences.

2.3.2 Evaluation Metrics

Automatically generating note sequences from audio is part of the pipeline for our dataset, so it is important to consider what metric to use in evaluating the effectiveness of a transcription model. Bay et al. present a method to standardize the evaluation of multiple-f0 estimation systems which has become widely used among polyphonic piano transcription models [18]. An F-Measure score, specifically F1 or harmonic mean, is defined to evaluate a set of predictions against a label set, by finding the precision and recall which is used to calculate the F-Measure, defined as seen in Figure 2.

Piano transcription systems [19, 20, 21] build on this evaluation metric by applying it to different features of the note. These different features often include the note onset, offset, and velocity, the last of which can be considered constant over the duration of the note since the piano doesn't support dynamic adjustment after the key has been pressed. Using these features, three F1 Scores are calculated. The first of these is the note onset F1 score will only compare the start of each note. This is the baseline metric and does not consider the length of the note or velocity. The following two metrics build on this by first adding the offset, then the offset and velocity. We will be using only the note onset f1 score to evaluate a transcription model as part of an automatic piano fingering pipeline, the justification of which will be discussed in the Methodology section.

As mentioned, the PIG Dataset [3] has become the standard evaluation dataset to measure the performance of models for the task of automatic piano fingering, further solidifying the set of well-defined metrics originally proposed [3], which were then expanded and organized into official test splits [4]. They outline several types of match rates to compare predicted finger sequences with multiple true-label annotations. A match rate is the percentage of the same label annotations between the prediction and a true-label sequence. The general match rate (GMR) is the average of this prediction over all available annotations for the piece. This is the most common metric used to evaluate a model. The recombination match rate (RMR), as shown in Figure 3, creates the closest match to the prediction using several ground truths, and can only switch between ground-truth sequences on a note that is mutually agreed upon. High match rate (HMR) picks the match rate score of the closest ground truth to the estimation. Soft match rate (SMR) checks if each label belongs to at least one ground truth. Finally, the change position rate (CPR) measures the amount of hand position changes such as finger crossings, normalized with the CPR of expert annotated scores.

Figure 3: Edit costs for the recombination match rate [3]

2.4 Hand-Pose Estimation

Hand-pose estimation, gesture recognition, and hand tracking are widely-research tasks in computer vision and can be applied to many applications, including interactive Augmented Reality (AR) and rendering [22], real-time sign language interpretation [23], and human-computer interaction [24]. For piano fingering, hand-pose estimation accuracy is the most important factor, followed closely by inference speed, given that it is applied to a large set of video files. Other considerations in hand tracking such as the ability to run on edge devices and the usage of depth sensors are not relevant.

The data being used for the automatic piano fingering dataset proposed in this thesis is based on pre-recorded videos, meaning that we cannot adjust the camera/recording settings in a way that would enable or optimize hand detection. For this reason, many existing systems for hands [25, 26, 27] cannot be implemented, as they require a depth sensor to perform any type of pose estimation.

MediaPipe Hands is a real-time hand-tracking system that can outline 21 landmarks in a hand [28]. Implementing two models, it first applies palm detection to draw a bounding box, then a hand landmark model to draw the skeleton. It is a robust system that can accurately track hands from an image or video, the latter of which implements tracking to improve the results with movement. Built on top of the MediaPipe framework [29], it enables GPU inference which is used for our data

pipeline to prevent hand-pose estimation from becoming the bottleneck.

2.5 Piano Transcription

For the piano fingering pipeline, we want to use a transcription model that can generate note labels that can be considered as a true label, in substitution for MIDI files. Many systems have been proposed for piano transcription, and so they will be compared on an accuracy-based score, as discussed in the previous metrics section.

Work by Moorer et al. proposed a bandpass filtering system to extract harmonic data but is limited by the ability to distinguish a note fundamental that is coincident with another note’s harmonic [30]. Multiple acoustic models have since been proposed in the time domain [31] that demonstrate a significant improvement in accuracy, as well as the frequency domain [32, 33]. Graham et al. comment that previous such works are limited by transcription algorithms following the theoretically grounded but unnecessary assumption that pitch arises from harmonic components [34]. They follow this up by presenting Support Vector Machines (SVMs) to classify frame-level note sequences that surpass previous works.

As with the sequence models for automatic piano fingering and many other applications, the commodification of deep learning completely transformed the research on transcription models. Applying computer vision models to spectrograms greatly increased the performance compared to previous models based on harmonic rules. Hawthorne et al. present a system that uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to first predict onset events, and then classify pitch within this frame [20]. Since frame hop size limits the ability to accurately predict note onset time, [19] presents a system trained by regressing precise onset and offset times of notes and shows that this outperforms the previous method on the onset F1 score, which is the most desirable for our implementation.

2.6 Piano Grid Detection

An ideal piano grid detection system would be able to take in a video frame where the keyboard is visible and automatically distinguish keys with accurate bounding boxes. In some cases where the camera is not positioned directly above the piano, homography transforms will be needed, although we do not consider this for the scope of this thesis.

One related task is detecting piano keys pressed in a video. Systems applied to this task need to perform some style of piano grid detection, but often make assumptions based on the recording style, and are more focused on light reflection to detect key presses [35].

Moyorssef et al. proposed a method to apply a grid to videos from the YouTube creator Rousseau, with the objective of estimating finger labels in note sequences [17]. The assumptions made to apply the piano grid, such as evenly dividing the width of the frame and finding the key bed using the highest brightness region hold up for Rousseau videos because of the high quality but are not robust enough to detect the grid in other content creators.

Since there is not any previous work that presents a solution equipped for the dataset that we wish to create, a novel method for piano grid detection is presented as described in the Methodology section to follow.

Chapter 3

Methodology

The full pipeline is visualized as seen in Figure 4. For each video, we first check if accompanying MIDI files are provided. If provided, we align the MIDI start times with the audio. If not, a transcription model is used to generate the note sequences. Hand-pose estimation is then applied to the video and saved to a CSV. Piano grid detection is performed to locate each piano key, and then by combining all the relevant information, fingers can be assigned to notes.

3.1 Gathering Data

As previously mentioned, the dataset is built using video piano performances gathered from YouTube. Firstly, we identified a set of candidate YouTube channels that could be used to extract technique. This comprised of 14 different performers totaling over 3,439 videos. From this selection, we then analyze and refine the set to 5 channels that produce consistent, high-quality performances that match video specifications we are looking for.

From this collection of videos, many will still need to be discarded due to the limitations of the pipeline, but the system is developed so that it will still be able to attempt feature extraction on these videos, and we can later discard the ones that do not give us accurate hand/piano information up to a certain threshold.

Figure 4: Pipeline flowchart

3.2 Alignment for Videos with MIDI

When creating a dataset for automatic piano fingering, the features will be a sequence of note events with corresponding finger labels. Some YouTube channels, such as Rousseau, provide MIDI files of each performance, which can be used to process the note sequences easily. This is the ideal case, although very uncommon among piano performance channels.

When the MIDI files are provided, an additional step is needed to align the notes of the MIDI with the audio. In the case of Rousseau, the MIDIs have a different length of silence before the first note when compared to the respective video, and this delta is not consistent across videos. To resolve this, we calculate the first estimated note onset in the audio from the video and compare it to the first note onset in the MIDI. The YouTube clip can then be trimmed accordingly so that both files are aligned.

In order to validate that the alignments are being performed correctly, a human-in-the-loop program was developed so that each pair of aligned MIDI files and video

could be inspected by the user, and either approved or re-aligned with a given delta.

As a preprocessing step for training models, we convert this MIDI format to note sequences in a tab-delimited text format. The values recorded for each note are ID, onset_time, offset_time, spelled_pitch, onset_vel, and offset_vel. It will be sorted by onset time, and the two velocities will be the same for every note. Later in the pipeline, a "values" channel (left or right hand) and finger_number are added to each note. This follows the same format implemented by [3] and [4].

3.3 Transcribing Videos

In the more prevalent case where accompanying MIDI files are not provided for the piano performances, note sequences must be estimated using a piano transcription algorithm. Since finger labels will later be appended to these note sequences, we are most interested in the note onset estimation, as this will be when the finger is playing the note. Other values, such as the note velocity and offset estimations are not needed. As discussed in the State of the Art section, we implement the most accurate note onset transcription model [19] to extract the note sequences from each video. Using the videos that have provided MIDI files and have been aligned, we can measure the accuracy of this transcription algorithm, which will also be discussed in the Results section. Transcriptions are converted to the same text format described in the alignment section.

3.4 Piano Grid Detection

Before hand-position information can be processed, we need to accurately determine the key boundaries of the entire piano within a frame of the input video. We have seen in the State of the Art section that there is one existing system that proposes a method for this [17], although implementation details are currently insufficient and may not be generalizable to videos from various recording environments, as discussed earlier. For these reasons, we propose a novel method for estimating the key boundaries of a piano in a video frame.

Figure 5: Mean pixel brightness per row in the video frame, filtered by a generated hand histogram

3.4.1 Keyboard Vertical Cropping

We first want to identify the boundaries of the entire keyboard from the background, as well as the vertical separator between the white key bed and the black keys. We perform this by extracting the mean brightness curve along the y-axis, as seen in Figure 5. Agreeing with the initial step by [17] reference, we assume that the white key bed will be the region with the highest average brightness.

We can further guarantee this by cropping the brightness curve with hand position information. By running an initial preprocessing step where we detect hands over the entirety of a video and create a histogram of the y-coordinates of each hand landmark, we can crop the brightness curve to the region where the hands are most common, which will be on or around the keyboard for the whole video. This filtered curve will show three significant changes in brightness: the top of the keyboard, the bottom of the black keys, and the bottom of the keyboard. We then apply a step detection function to find these values.

Figure 6: Key Separation along black and white keys

3.4.2 Key Separation

To separate the white keys, we pick a pixel row along the key bed section that does not have any black keys, as seen by the blue line in Figure 6. When measuring the brightness of this pixel row, we will see many uniformly distributed minima, which correspond to the black space between each key. We then use a peak detection function to capture these minima.

As proposed by [17], a simpler method would be to divide the length of the image into 52 segments, given that the piano has 52 white keys and assuming the keyboard perfectly takes up the whole width of the image frame. This assumption, however, adds limitations to the number of videos that can be utilized, and so this novel “minima method” is proposed to create a larger and more reliable dataset.

To segment the black keys, we choose a similar pixel row on the black key bed and measure the brightness. Since the white keys and their dividers will interfere in this step, we apply a valley detection method to measure the width of each black key. We set a minimum valley distance so that the black spaces between white keys are not detected. Once the vertical cropping and key separation are finished, we have enough data to create an accurate polygon for each piano key.

Figure 7: Piano grid applied to input frame, black keys outlined in red, white keys in blue

3.5 Generating Hand Data

The MediaPipe API that we use to estimate hand-pose returns 21 landmarks for each hand, where each landmark has an x , y , and z component. Since z approximates the hand distance from the camera and we are only concerned about the placement of fingerings on piano key sections, we will discard this value, although this could be insightful for future piano technique projects as an estimation of a key being pressed. To prevent the hand-pose estimation from needing to be run multiple times if adjustments later in the pipeline are needed, we first run the MediaPipe API on each video and write a CSV file of all the relevant hand-pose estimation data, which consists of the frame number, number of hands, and the (x,y) coordinates of each fingertip per frame.

3.6 Finger-Labeling Notes

Given a sequence of notes, the bounding boxes of each piano key in the video, and the hand fingertips data for each frame, we can apply fingerings to the notes. For each note, first get the onset time and establish a tolerance window before and after this onset to check for a finger on the key during the window. The onset tolerance is set to 0.05 seconds by default, the same default used in the `mir_eval` library for the `transcription_velocity` metric [36]. This window is then converted to frames given the FPS of the input video, and these frames are retrieved from the generated hand

data file for this piece.

We choose to assign a note with the most common finger that is on top of the key boundary over the duration of the onset tolerance window. This excludes the technique where the finger is switched while the key is still pressed, which is relevant in the prediction of fingering for the notes afterwards but is a very uncommon technique. If there is no finger on this note during the window, we leave the note unlabeled. In the next section, we will discuss how the dataset can be refined based on the preference of labelling quality for each song.

To measure if a finger is on top of a key for each frame, we loop over the (x,y) coordinates of each fingertip and check which piano key to assign it to. For this, we use the shapely library to check if the coordinate is within the key polygon that we created during grid detection [37]. Shapely is a highly optimized library built on GEOS [38] in C++, and so checking this for every key polygon and then again for every fingertip per frame is not a performance concern. We do not, however, apply any tolerance to the key bounding boxes. Because of this, a fingertip in a frame will only be assigned to one key, and it must be exactly within the boundaries. Although this inevitably decreases the percentage of notes that are labeled per song, it ensures that labels are accurate and that false positives are reduced as much as possible. In this sense, we can validate that all the components are working accurately if a note is labeled. If any of the previous steps: grid detection, note transcription/alignment, or hand-pose estimation are inaccurate, there will likely not be a detected finger exactly on the correct key boundary during the short onset tolerance window of a note. We will discuss this validation in detail later in the Results section.

3.7 Removing Under Labeled Data

After all the pieces have been assigned finger-labeled note sequences, we can measure the percentage of notes in each song that have been assigned a label, which as discussed in the previous section is only the case if all components provide an accurate result. This provides us with an easy way to visualize and sort the data by

Figure 8: Fully processed video comparing active notes with finger-key placements quality. If the labelling percentage for a song is at or near zero, we can assume that at least one of the components (grid, transcription, alignment, hands) did not work at all. We will discuss the reason why these components may fail in the Limitations section, but at this step in the process, we can simply remove all the songs with very few labels. Subsections of the data can also be created with a desired percentage. We experiment with choosing different subsets during model training, as higher percent thresholds will reduce the overall dataset but ensure higher quality data is used. In the Results section, we provide insight into the histogram of note labelling percentage per song across the entire dataset.

3.8 Model Training

We implement the autoregressive neural networks proposed by [4] for the task of automatic piano fingering. Two versions of the model will be saved as the training is being run: one for each hand. The graph neural network encoder was selected since it is better able to represent polyphonic sequences using edges, and performed the best on the official [3] test set, as demonstrated by [4].

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Dataset

Table 1 compares our Youtube-generated dataset with the most recent advances in Automatic Piano Fingering (APF). It is built with an initial selection of 5 YouTube channels, without removing any videos that will not be usable for this dataset, hence the large drop-off from total to labelled notes. Even so, it clearly outlines that an automatic method to label notes using YouTube channels can create a larger dataset than existing state-of-the-art solutions. In addition, the PIG Dataset [3], Thumbset [4], and YouTube-generated data all consider different input formats to label notes and thus can be used collaboratively to create a more generalized system. The PIG Dataset contains pieces with multiple expert annotations, proving to still be the best benchmark for testing models in this task.

Table 1: Dataset Size Comparison for Automatic Piano Transcription (APF)

Dataset	Total Notes	Labelled Notes
PIG Dataset	148,770	148,770
ThumbSet	271,680	178,737
APFD [17]	155,107	155,107 (noisy)
YouTube-Generated	1,619,312	514,712

Table 2 gives a detailed breakdown of the total and labelled notes per YouTube channel in our dataset. Rousseau is the only channel that has provided MIDI files, while the remaining are transcribed. Traum Piano has the lowest percentage of labelled notes, which is largely due to the style of videos; many of them have a side view of the piano as opposed to a top-down view, and even the framing of the piano in top-down views is quite varied per video. We will discuss in the Limitations section why the pipeline cannot generate data with these features.

Table 2: Note distribution by YouTube channel

Channel	Total Notes	Labelled Notes
Rousseau	296,296	131,800
AmiRRezA	111,829	71,652
Kassia	278,790	123,861
Patrik Pietschmann	244,746	158,149
Traum Piano	687,633	47,827
Total	1,619,312	514,712

4.2 Labelling Percentage

It is important to consider that there are a number of steps in the video analysis pipeline, most of which cannot be easily validated to make sure they work correctly for a large set of videos. To get a better understanding of this, we can instead look at the combined results of multiple systems. We'll first look at the labelling percentage, which will only produce good results if every system is working accurately, and then take a look at the transcription accuracy on videos with MIDI files, which will be able to validate that our note sequences are close to ground-truth.

To better understand the distribution of labelled and unlabeled notes in the dataset, we can observe a histogram of the number of songs that are within a range for the percentage of notes labelled. As seen in Figure 9, there is a large portion of songs with a labelling percentage over 80 and 90 percent. These will be the most valuable pieces to train a model with, and account for around 240,000 of the labelled notes,

Figure 9: Number of songs per label percentage

almost half of all labelled notes. There is also a very big portion of videos at or only slightly above 0%. With these videos, we can assume that at least one of the steps in the pipeline has failed. As discussed later in the Limitations section, there are many constraints to the current grid detection and hand-pose estimation which leads to this unlabeled data. The biggest commonalities in this unlabeled data are the camera orientations in Traum Piano videos, and the extreme hue color effects that interfere with hand-pose estimation.

4.3 Transcription Validation

Using the Rousseau data, we can measure the accuracy of the transcriptions using the MIDI labels. If we treat the aligned MIDI as the ground-truth labels, we can calculate the note onset accuracy from the estimated transcription. We use `mir_eval`'s transcription class to measure the note onset accuracy [36]. We are not interested in velocity or note offset estimation here, as they don't play as important of a role in assigning fingering information with notes.

The transcription accuracy average for all Rousseau pieces is 92.3%. When compar-

	gmr	hmr	smr	rmr	cpr
ArThumbLSTM-soft	64.082979	70.032417	83.606837	76.197673	1.044268
ArThumbLSTM	64.376029	70.593300	84.455241	76.580648	1.009667
ArThumbGNN-soft	65.236691	71.035931	84.815295	76.625344	0.966779
ArThumbGNN	64.698163	70.155646	84.749871	76.601972	0.980424
ArYouTubeGNN	46.470986	49.788501	63.762508	52.091265	0.577413

Figure 10: Trained model results in comparison with ThumbSet trained models [4]

ing this with the published results by [19] of 96.7%, we can be reasonably assured that the generated note sequences from the transcription model will be accurate enough to generate quality-fingered labelled data.

4.4 Model Results

In training the model, only a subsection of the data was used so that it could be trained on sequences of fully labeled data. Due to the scope of the thesis, training the model on partial annotations wasn't implemented, which would enable us to use the full dataset. As a result, a bit over 250,000 notes were used to train, only a small increase over previous datasets.

As mentioned in the Methodology section, the autoregressive model with a graph neural network (ArGNN) was implemented [4], as it performs the best on the PIG test dataset [3]. Figure 10 shows the initial results of training (labelled "ArYouTubeGNN") in comparison with models implemented by [4]. The ArGNN training on the YouTube dataset did not perform close to the same level as partial annotations finetuned to the PIG Dataset, primarily outlined in the general match rate (GMR). There are a few reasons for this. As mentioned, enabling training with partial annotations would greatly increase the capacity for the model to learn, and would more than double the number of labelled notes used to train. In addition, no data augmentation was performed, which as shown in the ablation results in [4], would lead to significantly improved results. Lastly, there was not enough time invested in training and adjusting the hyperparameters, so the results here are very

initial, and we expect much better scores with some easily implementable features.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The challenge addressed in this thesis is to create a set of generalizable methods to extract relevant piano technique information from video performances to create a comprehensive, multimodal dataset. We then discuss the usefulness of such a dataset in the task of automatic piano transcription. To prove the effectiveness of the pipeline on a large corpus of video data, an entire YouTube channel at a time was processed, ignoring the fact that many videos per channel would be incompatible based on the limitations of either the piano grid detection or the hand-pose estimation. As a result, a huge proportion of the songs and notes were completely discarded.

Many of these discarded piano performances would not provide any additional insight into piano technique. In some videos, the hands are completely removed or not visible within the camera frame, offering no knowledge of hand movement or fingering. In others, the angle of the camera may make it impossible to determine the assignment of fingers to keys. These are the types of videos that we don't intend to analyze at all for this task. There are, however, many variables in other videos that cause our system to not work as intended, even though we may deem that it is a suitable performance to extract technique information. We see these as areas of improvement to the pipeline, which can be appended without redesigning the system, that will increase the number of usable videos for this dataset, even without

increasing the set of YouTube channels to extract from.

When we noticed that a video failed in the pipeline for a specific reason, we purposely did not apply a fix that would only work for this video. We outline the limitation and implement a solution if possible. For cases where the solution does not work, or we have yet to implement one, we keep the video in our dataset, but use a labelling threshold that prevents the model from using this data in training. Building a robust system will yield more long-term results than applying quick fixes on a per-video basis.

5.1 Limitations

5.1.1 Piano Grid

The piano grid detection is the step in the pipeline that accounts for the greatest number of incompatible videos. Since we are very strict about only applying a finger label to a note if the finger is exactly inside the correct key boundary, an inaccurately applied piano grid on a video will result in an extremely low percentage of labelled notes. This is intended since we would rather value accurate labelling than very noisy data and it also provides an easy indicator as to which videos fail and why.

The piano grid detection expects a few things. Firstly, the camera view of the keyboard must be positioned directly above the piano. If it is at an angle or a side view of the keyboard, a homography transform would be needed to correct the perspective. This would be a useful feature to implement in the future but requires human intervention to hand-label the corners of the keyboard, given an input image. In addition, it expects a full 88-key piano that takes up the full width of the video frame. A human-in-the-loop system would also help fix incompatible videos in this case, but developing an automatic system to detect the number of keys and the width of the piano in the frame would not be trivial. Lastly, in separating the keys horizontally, an input frame without any hands in the way is needed. As discussed in the Methodology section, brightness curves are used to distinguish the separation between keys. If a hand were in the way, the peak detection would fail to separate

Figure 11: Piano grid limitations, video IDs: JVXo-IZumtA, cS4jcBd5Qrk

the keys. It is often hard to find an input frame in the video where the keyboard is clearly visible but the hands are not in the way, so the current solution is to take a reference frame per YouTube creator that is manually selected and does not contain hands, apply the key separation and store all relevant info in a JSON file, and for any future videos with this creator that fails to separate keys, apply the default grid from this JSON file. This works especially well for channels that maintain a very strict positioning of the keyboard across videos, such as Rousseau and Patrik Pietschmann. For cases such as Traum Piano, where there are often hands in the way of the frame and the location of the keyboard is not consistent per video, the pipeline fails to detect an accurate grid.

Figure 11 showcases some of these limitations. The first image has a crooked camera angle, bad lighting conditions, and hands in the way of the keyboard in this current frame. The second image is improved, but has a slight perspective shift due to the camera not being directly above the piano.

5.1.2 Hand-Pose Estimation

Another common limitation is hand-pose estimation using the MediaPipe API [28]. One example is the failure to detect hands in very fast motion, when they are

Figure 12: Incompatible lighting conditions for hand-pose estimation

performing large strides or other movements where the hand must quickly jump. In this case, we don't worry as much, since notes are rarely played when the hand is moving this fast.

The main limitation of the hand-pose estimation is in lighting conditions. Some YouTube channels apply heavy hues to the videos for artistic purposes, and these can sometimes completely muddle hand detection, as seen in the second image of Figure 12 where no hands are detected, while the image on the right misses the left hand due to low brightness. MediaPipe provides a pre-processing flag for minimum hand detection and tracking confidence, which we set to 0.5. Lowering this value might be able to produce results for these colorful videos but introduces the possibility of generating false positives. We have chosen to prefer accurate data over the potential to introduce noisy data, but this is a variable that is worth testing to further expand the dataset.

5.2 Future Work

We first discuss the improvements that can be made to the initial implementation of the system, then recapitulate some of the future use cases for the audio-visual dataset presented in this thesis.

The first planned improvement would be the automatic piano fingering model results. In the Results section, we outline a series of feature implementations that would significantly improve the results of this model with relative ease, as the scope of this thesis did not lend enough time for model experimentation.

In the dataset generation pipeline, the main limiter to creating a large amount of labelled data is the piano grid detection system. As discussed in the Limitations section, there are many constraints that a video needs to abide by in order to make it a valid data entry. Without ideal conditions, grid detection often fails, and without this, hand-pose estimations cannot be used to assign fingers to the note sequences. The main improvements that can be made are: making the key separation more robust with hands obscuring the vision, making it more tolerable to extreme lighting settings, and giving a human-in-the-loop option to mark keyboard corners, not only improving the cropping, but also enabling homography transforms when the camera angle is not ideal.

The hand-pose estimation model could also be improved. As mentioned, the MediaPipe hands model fails in conditions when the light is far from optimal. An experiment would need to be conducted that considers the minimum detection confidence and the tradeoff between false negatives and false positives.

Lastly, the pipeline should simply be expanded upon by adding large sets of new data. For the demonstration of this thesis, it was applied to five of the best-quality channels found for overhead videos on piano performance, but we initially identified 14 YouTube channels that create this style of videos as their primary content, which totals over 3,439 videos. Our dataset has only been generated from around one-third of this total, which means that there is a huge opportunity to keep developing and expanding this dataset.

As discussed in the introduction, there are many useful and innovative applications for the audio-visual dataset that we present. Generative models informed by physical limitations and action recognition could be developed to create more realistic and playable compositions. Education technologies could employ models trained on features extracted from hand movement to inform learners of posture improvements and fingering suggestions. Pre-established research tasks such as piano transcription and piano difficulty analysis could use these additional feature spaces to improve model accuracy, as hand movement is directly tied to note and performance information.

Promoting multimodal data analysis in music performance is a vital step to creating systems that can accurately model the physical intricacies of playing instruments and thus understand greater intentions behind music composition and performance. We hope that the contributions outlined in this thesis, including the produced dataset and a generalized technique extraction pipeline for videos may serve as a baseline for many such applications.

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